

DATA PRODUCT DESIGN FOR THE HIGH-RESOLUTION STEREO CAMERA ON CHANG'E-7.

Wangli Chen¹, Wei Zuo¹, Jianjun Liu¹ and Chunlai Li¹, ¹Key Laboratory of Lunar and Deep Space Exploration, National Astronomical Observatories, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100101, China (chenwl@nao.cas.cn, zuowei@nao.cas.cn, liujj@nao.cas.cn, licl@nao.cas.cn).

Introduction: The Chinese Chang'e-7 mission is scheduled for launch in 2026 and will conduct an integrated exploration of the lunar south pole, including orbiting, landing, roving, and hopping operations. One of the key scientific objectives is to investigate the occurrence state and abundance of water ice in permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) around Shackleton crater [1-3]. High-resolution imaging and topographic data are essential for understanding the geological context and supporting future exploration activities.

Instrument Overview: The High-Resolution Stereo Camera (HiRSC) onboard the orbiter is designed to acquire high-resolution panchromatic stereo images of the lunar surface, with a spatial resolution of up to ~ 1 m at 200 km altitude and ~ 0.5 m over selected regions at 100 km. The system consists of a forward-looking camera and a backward-looking camera, each integrated with a dedicated laser altimeter, enabling stereo imaging and precise ranging measurements for topographic reconstruction.

Data Processing and Product Levels: Scientific data from Chang'e-7 are processed by the Ground Research and Application System (GRAS), which is responsible for data reception, processing, management, and distribution. HiRSC data products are organized into three processing levels following the PDS4 standard [4].

Level 0 processing includes telemetry decoding, data unpacking, and decompression to generate raw image and engineering data. Level 1 processing reorganizes and standardizes the data, including sorting, merging, and orbit-based segmentation, producing structured datasets for further analysis. Level 2 processing includes radiometric calibration and geometric positioning. In particular, geometric processing provides geolocation information for both image pixels and laser measurements based on spacecraft ephemeris, attitude data, and sensor models.

Expected Products and Applications: The HiRSC stereo data will enable the generation of high-resolution digital orthophoto maps (DOMs) and digital elevation models (DEMs) of the lunar surface. These products will support precise landing site characterization, hazard assessment, and scientific investigations of lunar surface morphology, geological structures, and regolith properties. The dataset will provide an important high-resolution foundation for future lunar polar exploration and scientific studies.

Figure 1: (a) DEM of the candidate landing area for Chang'e-7; (b) Slope map of the candidate landing area.

References: [1] Yu H. et al. (2023) Journal of Deep Space Exploration. [2] Zhao F. et al. (2025) Remote Sensing. [3] Wang C. et al. (2023) National Science Review. [4] Tan X. et al. (2021) Space Science Reviews.